

SATISFACTORY

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CERTH ¹	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
SIGMA	Sigma Orionis SA	France
FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V	Germany
COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	Ecole Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
ISMB	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella sulle tecnologie dell'informazione e delle telecomunicazioni	Italy
ABE	Atlantis Engineering AE	Greece
REGOLA	Regola srl	Italy
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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
D	Deliverable
DCP	Dissemination and Communication Plan
DMP	Data Management Plan
EC	European Commission
EFFRA	European Factories of the Future Research Association
EU	European Union
IMS	Intelligent Manufacturing Systems
KPI	Key Performance Indicators
M	Month
NoI	Network of Interest
PFS	Presentation and Feedback Session
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SERP	Search Engine Results Page

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The present document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programme (H2020).

This document presents SatisFactory's Dissemination and Communication Plan (D6.3). The DCP is the strategy and implementation measures envisioned to efficiently communicate about project objectives and disseminate project outputs, in order to ensure the best exploitation of its results. The DCP is structured in order to answer the following questions – WHY, WHO, TO WHOM, WHAT, WHAT FOR, HOW, WHEN? – and to present relevant Key Performance Indicators (KPIs).

The DCP was created at M6. An updated version of the DCP is then provided together with each project periodic report about dissemination and communication activities (M12, M24, M36). This deliverable is the first update.

1. PURPOSE – WHY?

Before laying out the activities planned for dissemination and communication, it is useful to clearly identify the objectives of such activities.

1.1 DEFINITIONS OF “COMMUNICATION” AND “DISSEMINATION”²

According to the European Commission, project communication is “a strategically planned process, which starts at the outset of the action and continues throughout its entire lifetime, aimed at promoting the action and its results. It requires strategic and targeted measures for communicating about the action and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange”.

The dissemination of the project outputs is “the public disclosure of the results by any appropriate means (other than resulting from protecting or exploiting the results), including by scientific publications in any medium.”

1.2 OBJECTIVES OF DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION ACTIVITIES

The SatisFactory communication and dissemination objectives are:

- To promote EU research and innovation in manufacturing and ICT domains, and beyond;
- To raise awareness about innovative approaches for enhancing workplace attractiveness and key technologies for improving industrial development in Europe;
- To influence the attitudes of decision-makers towards a stronger support to European smart factories;
- To support SatisFactory activities and findings, making the results developed through the project available to the widest audience and enhancing the exploitation potential.

² The definitions of the key terms “communication” and “dissemination” used in this section are taken from the European Commission participant portal website.

https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/portal/desktop/en/support/reference_terms.html

2. DISSEMINATION PLAYERS – WHO?

WP6 is led by SIGMA, a company with an extensive expertise in communication and dissemination activities related to research and innovation projects. Most partners are engaged to support SatisFactory’s communication, dissemination and networking activities, for example by:

- disseminating links to SatisFactory’s activities through their own websites and social media;
- providing the task leader, SIGMA, with news on the project’s progress, which will be used to feed SatisFactory online and off-line communication;
- promoting SatisFactory during internal and external events.

Table 1 – WP6 efforts in person-month

WP6 EFFORTS IN PERSON-MONTH					
	T6.1 Dissemination & Communication Plans	T6.2 Project visibility & branding	T6.3 Project events and International Collaboration	T6.4 VR- enabled end- users training to SatisFactory solution	Total per partner
CERTH	2	0	3	8	13
SIGMA	4	11	12	3	30
Fraunhofer	0	0	0	0	0
COMAU	1	0	0	2	3
EPFL	4	4	2	0	10
ISMB	2	0	2	0	4
ABE	1	2	2	2	7
Regola	0	0	0	0	0
SUNLIGHT	1	1	2	2	6
GlassUP	1	1	2	0	4
Expected PM contribution per task	16	19	25	17	77

 = Task leader

3. TARGET AUDIENCES – TO WHOM?

The six main identified target groups are listed in the following table:

Table 2 – Target groups

	CATEGORIES	EXAMPLES OF MAIN STAKEHOLDERS
	Industry decision-makers	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - High-level representatives of manufacturing companies in various sectors (e.g. automotive, energy, etc.) - Professional organizations such as Intelligent Manufacturing Systems (IMS), and the European Factories of the Future Research Association (EFFRA)
	Research communities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Smart manufacturing researchers - Specific ICT research communities (e.g. IoT, Augmented Reality)
	Policy-makers and facilitators	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - EU Institutions (European Commission, European Science Foundation, MEPs) - National public authorities (industrial committees, ministry and regional councils) - Standardization Bodies (such as CEN, DIN)
	Pilot sites	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Operators in pilot plants (workers, technicians, managers, etc.)
	Related initiatives	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Related EU-funded projects - ETPs (MANUFUTURE technology platform) and clusters
	EU citizens	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Individuals and civil society

4. MESSAGES – WHAT?

Key information and solutions for building the industrial future of Europe will be disseminated during the project lifetime.

Table 3 – Key information to be disseminated

Key information and solutions to be disseminated by the project	
Information on:	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Research and innovation activities (implemented by the project, or relevant to the project area implemented by external stakeholders); • Project results;
Solutions for:	Innovative approaches and technologies for: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increasing factories productivity and efficiency; • Enhancing the attractiveness of working environment in factories.

Finally, the upgrading of manufacturing industry is expected to support the industrial economy and employment in Europe.

5. EXPECTED OUTCOMES – WHAT FOR?

The communication and dissemination plan is carefully designed to address the identified target groups in the most effective way. The expected outcomes of SatisFactory's communication include:

- a large number of stakeholders being more aware of ideas and technologies for building the industrial future of Europe;
- scientists, researchers and manufacturers convinced that they should pay a special attention to enhancing the quality and attractiveness of working environment in factories, and in making them attractive to young talents;
- if possible, economic and policy decision-makers encouraged in supporting the industrial economy and employment in Europe by promoting novel ICT technologies for industry;
- lastly, and above all, a broad dissemination of new, disruptive ideas, concepts and solutions for the enhancement of work life and manufacturing productivity.

SatisFactory key target audience and the expected impact of communication and dissemination activities are listed in the following table.

Table 4 – Expected impact on key target audiences

SATISFACTORY KEY TARGET AUDIENCES						
Expected impact:	Industry decision-makers	Research communities	Policy-makers and facilitators	Pilot sites	Related initiatives	EU citizens
• Will be more aware of ideas and technologies for building the industrial future of Europe	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
• Will help foster EU research and innovation on SatisFactory related technologies	✓	✓	✓		✓	
• Will be convinced to pay a special attention to enhancing the quality and attractiveness of working environment in factories	✓	✓		✓		
• Will support industrial economy and employment in Europe by promoting novel ICT technologies for industry	✓		✓			
• Will be directly affected by the outcomes of the research, and will provide feedback on project activities and results				✓		
• May adopt SatisFactory's technologies and solutions for improving factories efficiency and attractiveness	✓	✓				

6. TOOLS AND ACTIVITIES – HOW?

In order to meet the objectives previously defined, various tools and products related to communication and dissemination activities will be developed during the project lifetime. These tools and activities will provide accessible information to targeted stakeholders.

Figure 1 – Main dissemination materials and channels

The first step is to design the project **visual identity** (project logo, graphic charter, project templates) at M1 and M2. On this basis, the project **promotional materials** are created: a reference project presentation (M3), various templates (M3), a project flyer (M5), a video trailer (M7) and a brochure (M12-M13). **Online channels**, such as project website, social media, YouTube account, supplement the range of means of communication and dissemination. All along the project lifetime, the **publications** (news on the website, press releases, newsletters, research papers and public deliverables) inform the target audience about the project objectives, activities and findings. Finally, SatisFactory is promoted at external **events**. At least three Presentation and Feedback Sessions (PFS) will be made during the course of the project. **Networking activities** will result in the creation of a Network of interest (NoI) whose members (researchers, industrialists, etc.) may foster the impact and exploitation potential of the project.

Among those activities, materials already available can be found on the project website: <http://www.satisfactory-project.eu/>. They are described in detail in deliverable D6.4.

7. OVERALL DISSEMINATION AND COMMUNICATION MANAGEMENT – WHEN?

The main dissemination and communication activities will follow an incremental plan, of which the first year is shown below:

Table 5 – Main dissemination and communication activities by task for Year 1

Activity	Del.	Due date (DoA)
T6.1: Dissemination & Communication Plans		
Creating the Project website	D6.1	M6 (Done at M3)
Drafting the Data Management Plan (DMP)	D6.2	M6
Drafting the Dissemination and Communication Plan (DCP)	D6.3	M6
Drafting the Report on Dissemination Activities	D6.4	M12
T6.2: Dissemination & Communication activities		
Launching and feeding the project website and social media	<input type="checkbox"/>	X
Creating dissemination and communication material: flyer, videos, brochure, etc.	X	Brochure: M12
T6.3: Events and International Collaboration		
Networking with relevant organisations (IMS, EFFRA, AREA, etc.). Creating a Network of Interest (NoI).	X	X
Participating to external events (A&T exhibition, etc.). Preparing SatisFactory's participation to Hannover Messe.	X	Hannover Messe: April 2016: M16
T6.4: VR-enabled end-users training to SatisFactory solution		
Preparing the training material and scenarios	D6.5	(Later: M30)

7.1 ANALYTICS: IMPACT ASSESSMENT AND KPI'S MONITORING

This section recaps the expected impact of our communication and dissemination strategy (goals and objectives detailed in Section 1). A constant monitoring using appropriate tools

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(Web analytics, survey, etc.) and performance measurements (KPIs) will be done, in order to measure the quality and success of our communication and dissemination efforts, and to readjust actions whenever required. The following table lists the performance indicators and expected quantitative results for each communication and dissemination tools and activities.

Table 6 – Expected quantitative results

	EXPECTED QUANTITATIVE RESULTS			
	At M6	At M12	At M24	At M36
DISSEMINATION MAILING LIST				
• Number of subscribers	25	50	100	150
COMMUNICATION MATERIALS				
• Number of distributed project brochures/flyer	50	100	200	300
• Number of posters	10	10	20	20
WEBSITE				
• Position in SERPs on 3 predefined key expressions	Top 10	Top 5	Top 5	Top 3
• Number of unique visitors/month	100	200	250	300
• Minimum average visit duration	3'	3'	3'	3'
SOCIAL MEDIA CHANNELS				
Twitter				
• Number of followers	50	100	200	300
• Number of tweets per week	> 5	> 5	> 5	> 5
Facebook				
• Number of likes	15	30	60	100
• Number of posts per week	1	1	1	1
LinkedIn				
• LinkedIn subscribers	15	30	60	100
• Number of posts per month	2	2	2	2
YouTube				
• Number of views	50	200	400	600
• Number of videos	2	4	7	10
PRESS RELEASES AND PUBLICATIONS				
Press release				
• Number of diffusion platforms	3	5	8	10
Newsletter				
• Number of recipients	30	60	120	180

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PRESENTATION AND FEEDBACK SESSIONS

• Minimum number of participants	X	50	50	100
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7.2 TIMESCALE

The following timescale details when each communication and dissemination activity will be carried out. In the coming weeks and months next steps will include, inter alia, finalizing the brochure, preparing new videos, sending newsletters, organizing the first Presentation and Feedback Session. In addition, any relevant feedback will be taken into account to improve the future plans.

Figure 2 – Timescale

CONCLUSIONS

This document presents the Dissemination and Communication Plan of the SatisFactory project. The DCP is the strategy, previously defined at M6, which details the corresponding targets, messages and best-suited tools that will be coped with during the overall project period.

As an Innovation Action (IA), Satisfactory needs concrete market outlets for its products – a set of cutting-edge technologies to be integrated in factory production lines. The dissemination and communication strategy has (1) to allow all relevant stakeholders to be informed about the project activities and outputs, (2) to ensure the highest exploitation potential of SatisFactory products by maximizing information received by potential customers and (3) to support European research and innovation in manufacturing and ICT, thus contributing to enhance industry competitiveness in Europe.

This requires, among other things, creating a corporate identity, publishing promotional materials (such as flyers and press releases), using online communication (project website and social networks), building synergies with related on-going initiatives and participating in high-level events to present the project's progress. As shown in D6.4, the project is making steady progress toward the achievement of these dissemination and communication activities. Almost all the KPI that have been internally set up for the first period (M1-M12) – in order to foster the challenge of realizing an attractive and efficient communication – have been reached.

D6.3 “Dissemination and Communication Plan”, together with D6.4 “Report on dissemination activities, public participation and awareness”, will be reviewed on an annual basis (M12, M24 and M36). This review will take into account the envisioned KPIs to assess the efficiency and success of such activities. In case the project fails to achieve its targeted objectives, corrective measures will be implemented with the aim of ensuring the project effective dissemination of its results and ultimately the sustainability of project outputs.